

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Here is the May issue of J.UCS, again with what I would consider the typical coverage you would expect of a Journal of Universal Computer Science: one nice theoretical paper on a version of X-Machines, one conceptual paper in the important area of hypermedia and one paper discussing applications of KM (Knowledge Management) to environmental issues.

Hope you will enjoy this issue! Please keep submitting further nice papers, let me know if you are interested in joining our prestigious editorial board or acting as referee, and above all: tell your friends about J.UCS and make sure that someone is willing to pay US \$100.- for a campus license for J.UCS - quite a few colleagues have not even bothered to go through their complex library administration but have just taken the small sum out of their grant money! Note that subscriptions are NOT automatically renewed, so it is a one-time payment like buying a book.

We have been considering offering 25 free reprints of every paper if you are willing to pay \$100.- for a subscription for your campus. What do you think of this idea? Please let me know via hmaurer@iicm.edu. And please have another look at the subscription procedure as described under http://www.jucs.org/jucs_news

Thanks!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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